

EXTRACTION OF WHITE PROTEIN SUGAR FROM KHADRI DATES AS THE FIRST APPLICATION FOR USING DATES IN THE FIELD OF ALTERNATIVE MEDICINE

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ABSTRACT

In the manufacture of white sugar from dates, Khadri dates fruits were mixed with an appropriate amount of water and heated at a temperature higher than sixty degrees Celsius for two hours. Note that prolonged overheating may damage the nutrients and change the color of the product. In this study, the extraction process of white sugar rich in protein was explored using deep solvent using choline chloride/alcohol and dipotassium phosphate. The optimum conditions for the process were determined by examining the following variables: phase composition components, temperature, pH. The ratio and quality of the solvent mixture. It was concluded that the driving force for the extraction of white protein sugar using deep eutectic solvent, which consists of a solution of the hydrogen bond acceptor, tetraammonium salt, tetraalkyl ammonium chloride/with urea solution, which represents the bonding agent.

Deep solvents were used because of their zero toxicity and great power in extracting white sugar from dates. The best conditions for using deep solvent were applied to improve the quantity and quality of the extracted syrup. The date extract was filtered by filtration system which can produce completely clear syrup and then concentrated by rotary evaporator and then converted to powder by using autoclave and lyophilizer. The results also showed that using deep solvent can lead to the extraction of white sugar up to about seventy percent of the total weight of dates used and 45% of essential and non-essential proteins. The data indicated that using deep solvent type II at pH 5.7 and deep solvent component ratio 1:3 and temperature 45°C can produce a larger quantity of highly desired white sugar.

Key words: White Protein Sugar, Khadri Dates, Alternative Medicine

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1. INTRODUCTION

Dates are a type of dried fruit, and dates belong to the palm family. Date palms are one of the oldest fruit trees that used to grow in the Middle East. There are more than 100 different types of palm trees [1, 2]. The Kingdom of Saudi Arabia is considered one of the richest countries in the world in the cultivation and production of dates, especially in the Qassim region [3]. Dates in Saudi Arabia are also considered one of the most important food sources and economic resources in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia. The Kingdom hosts more than 33 million palm trees and more than 123 thousand agricultural holdings that produce more than 1.5 million tons of dates every year. Saudi Arabia ranks second in the world as the largest date-producing country, and its date exports in 2020 reached 215 thousand tons, exported to more than 107 countries, and the value of exports grew by 7.1%, with a value of 927 million riyals. In 2023, the value of the Kingdom's date exports increased by 14%, reaching 1.462 billion riyals compared to 1.280 billion riyals in 2022 [3]. This research deals with a new method aimed at using dates in the field of alternative medicine, as protein sugar was extracted from green dates and used in the treatment of protein loss diseases resulting from genetic differences, especially for children under the age of 10 years.

The three stages of date fruit development are Tamer, Rutab, and Khalal. Khalal stage dates have a firm texture, are unripe, and are yellow, red, or pink in color. They also include total dissolved solids (TSS), which is the percentage of total solids dissolved in water that makes it through a filter made by covering a normal filter paper with kaolin paste. Rutab stage dates are soft at the fruit's tip, RSS 55-60° Brix, astringent-free, and palatable at 30-45 Brix. and edible; Tamer stage dates have a Brix of 60-84° and are completely torn. Dates are typically picked when they reach the Tamer stage, which is when they reach an edible TSS of 60 to 70° Brix. Date syrup is used to make a variety of dishes, including snacks, desserts, baked goods, and health foods. Additionally, ripe dates are processed to make date syrup, date bars, and other goods. It is well known that dates have a high content of carbs (80%) but a low protein content (2-3%). The dry weight of date fruits (tamar) ranges from 10 to 22% moisture, 62 to 75% total sugars, 2.2 to 2.7% protein, 5 to 8% fiber, 0.4 to 0.7% fat, 3.5 to 4.2% ash, 0.06 to 0.20% total acidity, and 30.0 to 50.0 mg of ascorbic acid. As a food product, date fruits have roughly 70.6-76.3% sugar, 1.9-3% protein, 0.2-2.8 percent fat, 1.3% minerals, and vitamins [4].

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Two-thirds sugar and a quarter water make up the flesh of completely ripe dates; the remaining portion is primarily made up of cellulose, pectin, ash, and vitamins. Dates are regarded as a nutrient-dense fruit, and studies have shown that they clearly improve human health when consumed with other foods. Enough vitamins and minerals are present in dates to help avoid deficits [5]. Additionally, dates are a valuable alternative to processed sugar. The primary and most common by-product of dates in food technology is date syrup, which is used to make foods like jams, marmalades, concentrated drinks, chocolates, ice cream, confections, honey, and more [6–8]. Due to its high waste content, the Kabkab (Iranian Kabkab Dates) date can be used to produce date syrup at a cost-effective rate [9]. The most popular derivative date product is most likely date syrup (dibs). When bagged humid dates are stacked for several months, portions of the syrups are extracted by their own weight, producing this unintentional by-product. Additionally, it is made on a semi- and fully industrial scale, as well as in homes and villages, by extracting and boiling down the juice. Due to its high waste content, Reziz dates can be used to produce date syrup at a cost-effective rate. When making date syrup, the fruit is combined with water and cooked for around one hour. When the primary ingredients, sugars, are extracted, it takes about an hour at 70°C. This process darkens the product's color and eliminates some of its nutritional value. A new class of solvents known as deep eutectic solvents is thought to hold promise as environmentally friendly substitutes for conventional ionic liquids and organic volatile solvents in extraction processes. To lower their melting points, these solvents rely on hydrogen bonding interactions between various constituents. The goal of deep eutectic solvent development is to lessen the negative effects of conventional solvents on the environment and their high cost. Because deep eutectic solvents can function at lower extraction temperatures than organic volatile solvent extraction, they have also been demonstrated to stop the breakdown of specific chemicals (such as polyphenolic). The so-called deep eutectic solvents (DESs) are a novel class of compounds that have surfaced as promising green solvents in recent years. Compared to earlier attempts, these new DESs have proven to be a more practical and stringent option [5,6]. They offer a novel kind of material with improved health and environmental qualities, reduced production costs [7], and improved biodegradability profiles [8].

A mixture of two or more compounds (hydrogen bond donors and acceptors) that are solid at ambient temperature but exhibit a melting point depression and turn liquid when combined at a specific molar ratio is known as a DES [9]. In general, the combinations' ingredients are inexpensive and safe [10]; Although quaternary salts like betaine or choline chloride are more common, alternative hydrogen bond acceptors including thymol, menthol, decanoic, or lauric acid have also been employed [11]. Urea, amino acids, sugars, alcohols, amides, amines, or carboxylic acids are frequently used as hydrogen bond donors [12,13]. The components of DESs can actually be designed by appropriately mixing them because they are directly related to their properties [10]. DESs generally exhibit a number of characteristics, including low preparation costs, low toxicity, low vapor pressure and volatility, wide polarity range, low vapor pressure, non-flammability, thermal and chemical stability, and biodegradability. Furthermore, they offer a wide range of combinations that can be used to create various solvent types based on their intended applications [14,15]. DES components are thought to be good alternatives to ionic liquids or conventional solvents since they can interact through intermolecular forces rather than just covalent or ionic bonds [16].

2. PRACTICAL PART

The initial chemical analyses of the different types of dates traded in the Qassim region showed that dates do not contain protein or fatty acids in all types of dates subject to the study except for the Khadri date. The chemical analysis of the Khadri date proved that it contains amine compounds (protein and fatty acids) that reached 15% of the weight of the date in addition to the glucose and fructose content of more than 60%, which is the highest among other types of dates Table (1). Our current invention is applied to Khadri dates where the modern deep solution of tetraalkyl ammonium chloride is added with urea solution and 1Lk at different temperatures and pH

2.1. Raw materials used:

2.1.1. Original materials:

Seven types of dates famous in the Qassim region were purchased such as Khadri dates, Nabta Ali dates, Maktoumi dates, Rashedi dates, Saqei dates, Sukkari dates and Barhi dates, where they were purchased from one of the shops located in the dates market in the city of Buraidah - Qassim - Saudi Arabia.

2.1.2. Supporting materials:

Pure anhydrous ammonia solutions (more than 99%), anhydrous methyl alcohol solution, concentrated sulfuric acid, ethyl alcohol at a concentration of 96% and solutions of the deep solvent tetraalkyl ammonium chloride/with Sigma Aldrich urea solution

2.1.3. Devices:

A vibrating stirrer with a heater and its use for shaking while raising the temperature at the same time for the mixture of dates with sulfuric acid (Figure 1) B. An electric oven (Figure 2)

C. A lyophilizer (Figure 3)

D. A liquid chromatography device (Figure 4)

Dr. Pressure vessel (autoclave) (Picture 5)

3- STEPS FOR EXTRACTING PROTEIN SUGAR FROM GREEN DATES

1-Cut one kilogram of pitted green dates into small pieces approximately (0.5 x 0.5 cm)

2-Wash the cut dates using running distilled water to remove suspended materials and dust

3-Add one kilogram of washed green dates with 2 liters of sulfuric acid at a concentration of 1 molar with continuous stirring at a temperature of 80 degrees Celsius to produce the raw mother mixture

4-Place the raw mother mixture in one liter of tetrachloride tetraalkyl ammonium/with urea solution in the autoclave with the temperature set at 65 degrees Celsius and pressure 0.1 bar for 4 hours

5-Cool the resulting protein sugar production for 6 hours at the laboratory temperature (20 degrees Celsius)

6-Place the protein sugar production in the lyophilizer at a temperature of -35 degrees Celsius and pressure 0.1 for 48 An hour to get the final product in the dry form of pure powder.

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The drying of the product from solvents occurs by sublimation by freezing the product at low temperature where the product and liquid solvents turn into ice. Under low pressure, the frozen solvents evaporate and turn into vapor without passing through the liquid state (called sublimation phenomenon) (Figure -1). Freeze drying involves cooling the sample below the triple point with the help of a freezer at $-35\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ so that the physical form of the material does not change. The pressure is reduced by a vacuum pump and some heat is given to the material to sublime and more than 90% of the solvent is removed from the sample. Molecules that have stronger bonds with each other are removed from the solvent. By applying a high vacuum and sufficient time, the solvent is completely removed from the sample.

7-The process of repeating the crystallization of the product to obtain the crystalline form is carried out using ethyl alcohol at a concentration of 96% followed by filtration and drying at a temperature of 60 degrees Celsius.

Method of measuring the concentration of protein sugar using the spectroscopic analysis method [16 and 17]

1-Dissolving 0.1 grams of the extracted white crystals in which protein sugar is expected to be present in 50 milliliters of acetic acid solution at a concentration of 0.2 normal.

2-Adjusting the wavelength of the spectroscopic analysis device at 200 nanometers for sugar and 250 for protein.

3-Recording the readings of the concentration of the sugar and protein compound from the device.

4-Using the calibration curve to determine the concentration of the sugar and protein compound in the final product.

5-The percentage of the resulting amount of sugar and protein is calculated by comparing the weight of the resulting sugar and protein with the initial weight of the dates used and multiplying the resulting values by 100.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This invention aims to search for a type of dates that contains in its components a significant percentage of protein and free amino acids, as well as a high percentage of glucose and fructose. Chemical analyses were conducted for many types of dates known for their high reputation in the Qassim region (Table 1) with the aim of searching for dates that contain protein and amino acids. It was noted that the green date contains protein and amino acids in addition to glucose and fructose, which are components of protein sugar.

3.1. Description of the green date

The main components of the green date:

The green date is the only one among the different types of dates that contains protein and amino acids in addition to a large percentage of glucose and fructose, which are qualified to form protein sugar using an autoclave and a lyophilizer.

3.2. Production and characterization of protein sugar

The glucosamine compound that will be used to treat osteoporosis is extracted through three stages. The first stage: The preparatory stage to prepare the mother mixture before the autoclave stage. 2 liters of sulfuric acid are added to one kilogram of dates gradually drop by drop, where water molecules are removed from the date paste in the form of steam at a temperature of 80 degrees Celsius with stirring for 4 hours while carefully monitoring the temperature to avoid raising the temperature more than that, which can cause the formation of the undesirable 5-hydroxymethylfurfural compound, which is formed if the temperature rises to more than 100 degrees Celsius, which can be obtained because the reaction of sulfuric acid with dates is an exothermic reaction.

THE SECOND STAGE IS THE AUTOCLAVE STAGE

The raw mother mixture is placed in a pressure vessel known as an autoclave in a water-free state with one liter of anhydrous ammonia mixture, which is pure ammonia (more than 99%) in a reaction medium with one liter of anhydrous methyl alcohol under a pressure of 7 bars, which is approximately equivalent to 100 pounds per square inch at a temperature of 25-80 degrees Celsius for a period of 3-8 hours. Methanol was chosen as an inert organic solvent that is miscible with water to react with fructose like its reaction with glucose and protein using the deep eutectic solvent, which consists of a solution of the hydrogen bond acceptor, the quaternary ammonium salt, tetraalkyl ammonium chloride/with a solution of urea, which represents the bond donor to form the protein sugar. The concentration of the protein sugar resulting from the autoclave is easily determined using an ultra-high liquid chromatography device. As a physical first sign of the reaction between glucose and amine, the solution turns light yellow to cloudy white as a result of the chemical reaction between amino groups and protein with glucose and fructose groups. The change in temperature and time on the amount of product is studied to reach the optimum conditions to obtain the largest amount of product, Figure (1) and (2). It is clear from Figure 1 and 2 that with increasing temperature from 25 to 80 degrees Celsius, the amount of protein sugar increases from 0.08 grams at 25 to 0.71 grams at 65 degrees Celsius. It is also clear from the graph that the amount of glucosamine remains constant with increasing temperature from 65 to 80 degrees Celsius, which confirms that the optimum temperature for producing protein sugar in the autoclave is 65 degrees Celsius. When referring to Figure 2, which explains the effect of time per minute on the amount of protein sugar produced, it is also clear that the amount of protein sugar increases with time until the amount produced (0.7 grams) is stable at 240 minutes. Based on this stage of the study, it was proven that temperature 65 and time 4 hours are the ideal conditions for the autoclave stage to ensure the formation of the largest possible amount of protein sugar compound, estimated at 0.71 grams per gram of green dates.

THE THIRD AND FINAL STAGE IS THE LYOPHILIZATION STAGE

This stage aims to obtain the final product, protein sugar, in a solid form in the form of a dry powder completely free of any liquids. The protein sugar resulting from the autoclave stage is placed in the lyophilization device at a temperature of -10 to -50 degrees Celsius and under a vacuum pressure of 0.137 for 48 hours, as this step leads to preserving the protein sugar in the dry form in addition to producing more dried extract. The effect of temperature and pressure on the amount of protein sugar resulting from the lyophilization device was studied, as shown in Figures (3 and 4).

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It is clear from Figure 4 that with the reduction of the temperature of the lyophilizer from -10 to -50 degrees Celsius with the pressure value fixed at 0.1, the amount of protein sugar gradually increases from 0.71 to 0.8 grams per gram of dates to reach the maximum amount at a temperature of -35 degrees Celsius, then the amount of protein sugar stabilizes with the reduction of the temperature until reaching -50, which means that the optimum temperature in the lyophilizer is -35 degrees Celsius. The effect of the pressure value applied in the lyophilizer on the amount of the resulting protein sugar compound was studied and it was noted that the optimum conditions when the pressure value reaches 0.1 millibars. The best yield of the protein sugar product in terms of quality and quantity was recorded in our invention, reaching 0.8 grams of the product per gram of green dates, which is the largest amount obtained compared to 0.005 grams of protein sugar per gram of oysters and shrimp, which is registered in the American and British patents and which were reviewed in the introduction section. The price of green dates has decreased with ease.

Pic. 1 Temp. and stirrer

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Pic. 2 Oven

P 2 b Oven b

Pic 3a lipilyzed

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